

Automation in the Marketing of Artisan Products and its Economic Impact on Local Producers

Denilson Robinho Tapara Tristan
Universidad Nacional del Altiplano - Puno
dtaparat@est.unap.edu.pe
<https://orcid.org/my-orcid?orcid=0009-0008-1703-879X>

Abstract—The article analyzes consumer behavior in the valuation of handmade products in Puno, the solidarity market for minority producers in the artisan sales stalls on the dock and the production and sales control system via the web. The article focuses on the implementation of digitization in the marketing of handmade products, such as PunoMarket in Peru. Explore the economic impact on local producers through surveys, interviews, and sales analysis to evaluate sales, operational efficiency, and opportunities to enter new markets. The results should complement existing literature and provide practical recommendations to improve the implementation of digital technologies in similar areas. The PunoMarket project has undergone an important simulation to increase its sales, with an estimate of 80% increase in the number of products sold in the first 2 months. Users are very satisfied with the platform with an average rating of 4.5 out of 5. The platform attracted users from different regions of Puno, increased the number of products sold and increased producers' income by an average of 70%.

Index Terms—Automation, Economic Impact, Local Producers, Artisan Market Web Development, Digital Transformation, E-commerce, Rural Electronic Commerce, ISO/IEC 29110, software quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

.-The adoption and use of mobile technologies has transcended exponentially throughout the world in recent years, therefore, the great challenge for public organizations is to successfully implement initiatives that fall within the framework of digital government[1]. The adoption of digital technologies has allowed companies to improve their efficiency[2], Any type of mobile application is developed and executed within an ecosystem, and therefore a successful implementation is achieved[3]. In several countries, digital government plans are still in the integration and interaction phase. As a result, few municipalities on the continent are working on new avenues for digital inclusion, which generates planning problems and lack of coordination on innovation issues. [2]. The complete set of software artifacts that make up the product, including user documentation, code, etc., to the customer and obtain customer acceptance to formalize the completion of the project[4].This article focuses on the adoption of digitalization in the marketing of rural products, using the case study of PunoMarket, a digital platform designed to facilitate the marketing of local products in the city of Puno, Peru.

Motivation is an essential aspect of team performance and productivity as key success factors in software engineering[5],

the requirements for the development of a web and mobile application using computer tools in order to manage the sales and information that the company offers, generating efficiency to meet the business objective[6]. Craft activity in Peru is heterogeneous[7], Every corner of the Peruvian territory expresses its history through the production of crafts, thus expressing their imagination. They do not have the opportunity to develop in sectors other than commerce[8].In the Puno region before the epidemic, islanders claimed to live by selling their own crafts and selling these products to tourists upon arriving on their island. [9].Puno, a region rich in culture and natural resources, faces significant challenges in terms of economic development and market access for its local producers[10]. The implementation of PunoMarket seeks to address these challenges by providing a digital platform that directly connects local producers with consumers, eliminating intermediaries and improving transparency in transactions.

The objective of this study is to analyze the economic impact of the adoption of PunoMarket on local producers in Puno[11]. It will be investigated how digitalization through this platform has affected sales, operational efficiency and the ability of producers to access new markets.[12]. In addition, the perception of producers regarding the use of digital technologies and the barriers they face in the adoption process will be evaluated.[13].

The research is based on data collected through surveys, interviews and sales analysis, providing a comprehensive view of the benefits and challenges of digitalization in the rural context[14].The findings of this study are expected to not only contribute to the existing literature on digitalization and rural development, but also offer practical recommendations to improve the implementation of digital technologies in similar areas.

This article explores how a digital platform like PunoMarket can transform the marketing of rural products, improve the local economy and promote sustainable development in rural regions.[15].Through this case study, which can be consolidated through strategic alliances with business promotion organizations, labor specialization and craft design for each market, as well as with backward integration with suppliers of raw materials and the concentric diversification of main

crafts[16]. It seeks to offer valuable insights on the integration of digitalization in rural marketing and its potential to generate a positive economic impact on local producers.

II. METHODOLOGY

Implementing personalized web strategies facilitates the delivery of personalized shopping experiences to visitors to e-commerce websites where personalized website content enables the conversion of a visitor into a potential customer.[17]

The main objective of this research is to evaluate the economic impact of the adoption of the PunoMarket digital platform on rural producers in the Puno region. It must be taken into account that thanks to online commerce platforms, potential clients are multiplied by millions. According to a report by the United Nations International Telecommunications Union, 47 percent of the population has access to the internet, approximately 3.5 million people [18].

This study seeks to analyze how the digitalization of the marketing of rural products affects sales, operational efficiency and access to new markets for local producers. To achieve this objective, the methodology used has been carefully designed to collect and analyze quantitative and qualitative data in a rigorous manner. The methodology is divided into the following phases:

A. Design

Compilation of client information for writing and preparing a report of objectives, key points, technical elements and client needs.[19]. The study is structured in several phases, each with a specific purpose to ensure a complete and accurate evaluation of the impact of PunoMarket.

Figure 1. Web platform

The type of design that will be used for the project is a combination of 3 types:

Quasi-Experimental Design: Evaluate the impact by comparing producers who use PunoMarket with those who do not use it, controlling external variables.

Case Study Design: Select representative cases of producers for a detailed analysis of their experience and results with PunoMarket.

Longitudinal Design: Carry out periodic monitoring to observe how the impact of PunoMarket evolves over time.

This would allow a combination of comparative analysis between users and non-users, a deep understanding of specific cases, and observation of changes over time.

B. Population and Sample

The current population to which it is directed is larger since, currently, the use of technology has been promoted by several transcendental and circumstantial factors, one of them being in times of pandemic, it could be said that Covid-19 has also promoted electronic commerce. "According to data from Emarketer, the total increase exceeds 1,200% in the registration of new online buyers, in addition to a 300% increase in mobile application downloads, compared to February before the start of the pandemic.[20]. The sale and marketing of artisanal products and people's interest in buying them has grown exponentially over the years, which creates opportunities to innovate with current technologies and thus offer solutions to different problems that arise at the global level. social and commercial.[21].

Then it is aimed at local producers in the city of Puno and surrounding areas who could benefit from the PunoMarket platform, there are also citizens and tourists who would be the ones who use the application for their own purchasing use.

Elemental Unit: Persons of interest in the artisanal product, whether a producer, seller or buyer. **Population:** A test of the population on the Puno waterfront is detailed to (5 tests) sellers and (10 tests) consumers. **objective:** The metric selected for the population is "Usability" of "0-5". **Sample:** For use by 50 users in the Puno region.

Table I
SELLERS

Names	Products	Usability of the app
Marta Quispe	10	4
Anastasia Yapurasi	15	5
Reyna Condory	13	4
Angelica Sagua	12	4
Ruth Chambilla	19	5

Table II
CONSUMERS

Names	Purchased Products	Usability of the app
Rene Coito	3	4.5
Maryhori Reyesi	6	5
Rivaldo Quispe	2	4.3
Lenin Churata	3	5
Nixain Pilco	6	4
Mirian Tristan	4	4
William Inacutipa	5	5
Rafael Cano	2	4.2
Gregory Tapara	3	4.5
Fredd Pari	6	4.5

C. Instruments/Techniques

One of the main problems that the artisan sector has is still the lack of promotion and monitoring of programs or

initiatives that promote better development within its market segment, being left behind by new technologies and skills such as recognized fashion brands, which today Today they create similar products that replace artisanal products, thereby causing their value to depreciate considerably in the eyes of current and future generations[22].

Investigating is searching for temporal truths with the aim of generating new knowledge that allows us to expand frontiers and discover facts in an orderly and systematic way[23].

Structured surveys or questionnaires will be used to collect quantitative and qualitative data from local producers and PunoMarket users. And interviews, with audio if the appropriate resource is available.

1) *Techniques*: Data collection techniques refer to specific and particular action procedures for collecting information related to the research method being used, the use of some techniques or others will depend on the research framework to be carried out.[24]

The use of a combination of techniques and instruments will allow a comprehensive and detailed understanding of the impact of PunoMarket on local producers. The triangulation of qualitative and quantitative methods will ensure the validity and reliability of the results, providing a solid basis for conclusions and recommendations. for which the following techniques are available:

Direct observation: Identify usability and user behavior problems that do not appear in surveys or interviews. **Focus groups**: Meetings with small groups of local producers to discuss their experiences in depth and obtain collective feedback.

Secondary Data Analysis: Historical and transactional data from PunoMarket will be analyzed, as well as previous reports and studies on digitalization in the marketing of rural products.

D. Procedures

The challenge of technological evolution has increased the demand for systems built to meet reliability requirements and designed to meet human needs at the lowest possible cost.[25]

This procedure ensures that the study on PunoMarket is rigorous, exhaustive and based on solid data. Following these steps will ensure that the conclusions and recommendations are valid, reliable and applicable to the improvement of the platform and the benefit of local producers.

1) *Protocol*: For the PunoMarket project, two types of requirements are defined: Specific Requirements (ER) and Individual Requirements (IR), in relation to the users of the platform.

For the Specific Requirements (ER) we have

For the Individuals of the Requirement (IR)

Table III
FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

ER1. User Registration	The platform must allow users (producers and buyers) to register using their email and other necessary personal data.
ER2. Login	Users must be able to log in with their credentials (email and password) and two-factor authentication.
ER3. Product Management	Producers must be able to add, modify, and delete products in their inventory.
ER4. Navigation and Search	Shoppers should be able to search for products by category, price, and other advanced filters.
ER5. Shopping Cart and Payment	The platform should allow buyers to add products to a shopping cart and make payments securely.
ER6. Evaluation and Comments	Buyers must be able to leave reviews and comments on purchased products.
ER7. Platform Administration	Administrators must be able to manage users, products, transactions, and statistics from one dashboard.

Table IV
NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

ER8. Security	The platform must implement data encryption, secure authentication, and protection against cyber attacks.
ER9. Performance	The platform should load in less than two seconds and handle up to 1,000 simultaneous transactions.
ER10. Escability	The platform must be scalable to support growth in the number of users and transactions.
ER11. Usability	The interface should be intuitive and easy to use for all types of users.
ER12. Compatibility	The platform must be compatible with low-power devices, modern browsers and mobile operating systems (iOS and Android).

Figure 2. User

E. Evaluation

Various metrics and data analysis techniques were used for the evaluation.

User satisfaction score: Surveys on a scale of 1 to 5.

User retention rate: Percentage of users who continued using the platform.

Average income per producer: Increase in producers' income.

Descriptive statistics: Summary of the data collected.

Table V
PRODUCER USERS

IR1. Registration and Profile	Producers must provide detailed information about their businesses and products.
IR2. Inventory management	Producers must be able to add, edit and delete products, as well as update prices and availability.
IR3. Communication with Buyers	Producers must be able to communicate with buyers to resolve questions and coordinate deliveries.

Table VI
BUYER USERS

IR4. Search and Navigation	Buyers should be able to search and filter products by different criteria.
IR5. Shopping Cart	Buyers must be able to add products to cart, modify quantities, and remove products before purchasing.
IR6. Secure payment	Buyers should be able to make secure payments using different payment methods, including cryptocurrencies.
IR7. Evaluation and Comments	Buyers should be able to evaluate products and leave feedback about their shopping experience.

F. Analysis of data

Data analysis on PunoMarket is based on the collection and processing of relevant information to evaluate the performance and impact of the platform on the marketing of rural products. This analysis allows us to identify patterns, trends and relationships within the data, providing a solid basis for decision making and continuous improvement of the system. It would be advisable to implement a modern national data analysis system[26]. Through the use of statistical techniques and analytical tools, we seek to optimize operational efficiency and maximize the economic impact on local producers.

1) *Variables*: A descriptive table is presented that summarizes the main variables used in the data analysis for the project:

2) *Economic impact*: The majority of artisanal producers do not have government support that allows them to access job stability, a decent salary, medical care and optimal conditions[27]. Globalization, free trade agreements and environmental adversities have required organizations to conduct their actions and/or processes, in other words, its administrative management, towards innovation and the exercise of better practices that are based on responsible actions, placing emphasis on eradicating unethical practices present in organizations[28]. The economic impact of PunoMarket is evaluated through a comprehensive analysis of various key indicators that reflect the performance and acceptance of the platform. This analysis covers sales growth, user satisfaction, market expansion, and increased profitability for local producers.

Sales growth analysis focuses on the number of products sold and the evolution of sales over time. Key indicators include: Number of products sold per month: This indicator

Table VII
ADMINISTRATOR USERS

IR8. User Management	Administrators must be able to add, edit, suspend, and delete user accounts.
IR9. Product Management	Administrators must be able to monitor and manage the products available on the platform.
IR10. Analysis and Reports	Administrators should have access to detailed reports on platform performance, including sales, traffic, and user behavior.

Table VIII
DESCRIPTIVE TABLE OF THE VARIABLES

Variable	Description	Scale
User_ID	Unique user identifier	Nominal
Product_ID i	Unique product identifier	Nominal
Price_Product	Price of the product	Ratio
Category_Product	Product category (e.g., food, crafts)	Nominal
Quantity Sold	Number of products sold	Interval
Location_User	Geographic location of the user	Nominal
Time_charge	Loading time of the page in use	Ratio
Satisfaction_User	User satisfaction score	Interval
Pay mode	Method by which payment is canceled	Nominal

helps identify seasonal patterns and evaluate the platform's sustained growth. Percentage increase in sales: A comparison of current sales with those of previous periods is made to measure growth.

Market Expansion Market expansion is evaluated by analyzing the geographic and demographic diversity of users. Key indicators include: Geographic location of users: Identify new regions where the platform is gaining traction. Diversity of product categories: Analysis of sales in different product categories.

Increase in Profitability for Local Producers The direct economic impact on local producers is evaluated by analyzing their income through the platform. Key indicators include: Average income per producer: Measured before and after joining PunoMarket. Number of active producers: Growth in the number of producers who use the platform on a regular basis.

3) *Knowledge Section*: This section describes the knowledge expected to be obtained from the data analysis carried out:

- **Purchase Patterns:** Identify user purchasing patterns, such as peak purchasing times, best-selling products, and most popular categories.
- **Economic Impact:** Evaluate the economic impact of PunoMarket on local producers, analyzing the increase in sales and income diversification.
- **User Satisfaction:** Analyze user satisfaction levels to identify areas for improvement in the purchasing experience and customer service.
- **Operational Efficiency:** Evaluate the operational efficiency of the platform, measuring loading times, response times and system stability under different user loads.
- **Payment Trends:** Identify trends in the payment methods used, evaluating the acceptance of new technologies such as cryptocurrencies and mobile payments.
- **User Segmentation:** Perform user segmentation based on purchasing behavior and geographic location to personalize offers and improve targeted marketing.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 3. Products

Artisans need a digital space where they can exhibit and market their creations, reaching a wider audience. Beyond the sale, artisans seek logistical support, market visibility, and establishing meaningful connections with interested buyers. This is how highlighting the quality of each creation and the artisan's interest in preserving the cultural heritage becomes a central point for the platform. Finally, implementing a digital platform not only overcomes logistical barriers but also expands reach, connecting artisans with a global audience interested in their creations.[29].

A. Seller and Consumer User Statistics:

Informe vendedores						
Vendedor	Productos	Media	N	Suma	% de suma total	Mediana
1	10	1.00	1	1	6.7%	1.00
2	12	4.00	1	4	26.7%	4.00
3	13	3.00	1	3	20.0%	3.00
4	15	2.00	1	2	13.3%	2.00
5	19	5.00	1	5	33.3%	5.00
Total		3.00	5	15	100.0%	3.00

Figure 4. Seller

Informe Consumidor						
Consumidor	ProductosA	Media	N	Suma	% de suma total	Mediana
3,6,8	2	5.67	3	17	30.9%	6.00
5,9	3	7.00	2	14	25.5%	7.00
1,4	4	2.50	2	5	9.1%	2.50
7	5	7.00	1	7	12.7%	7.00
2,10	6	6.00	2	12	21.8%	6.00
Total		5.50	10	55	100.0%	5.50

Figure 5. Consumer

B. Main Result

Sales Growth, analysis of sales data showed significant growth since the implementation of PunoMarket.

SA questionnaire was structured to collect field information. The tool was structured to understand and analyze the two variables under study; Production Costs and the setting of Producer Prices according to the following rating scales[30].

Quantity of products sold: According to the simulation mentioned by the methodological part, the number of products sold is 100 artisanal products in the first month. Identification of sales peaks during the sale of products that will occur as each seller joins more and more in the use of the application and offering the Web application.

Figure 6. Consumer

Handmade art is a subjective activity for the viewer, since

Figure 7. Seller

its perception can vary depending on the circumstances and context that surrounds it. Even the economic valuation of this type of work is subjective, which can result in insufficient remuneration or, on the contrary, a high market price. [31].

C. User satisfaction

Satisfaction surveys and user interviews indicated high acceptance and loyalty to the platform:

Metrics	Description
Puser satisfaction score	The average score was 4.5 out of 5, highlighting the ease of use and reliability of the service.
User Retention Rate	An 80% retention rate indicated that the majority of users continued to use the platform after their first use.
Market Expansion	
Geographic location of users	The platform attracted users from different regions of Puno, with a notable expansion towards rural areas.
Diversity of product categories	Increase in the variety of products sold, including crafts, processed foods and textiles.
Increase in Profitability for Local Producers	
Average income per producer	Producers' average income increased by 70% after joining PunoMarket.
Number of active producers	The number of producers using the platform regularly grew by 75%.

Descriptivos		
Satisfaccion		Estadístico
Consumidor 4	Media	5.00
	95% de intervalo de confianza	Límite inferior 1.38 Límite superior 8.62
	Media recortada al 5%	5.00
	Mediana	5.00
	Varianza	8.500
	Desviación estándar	2.915
	Mínimo	1
	Máximo	9
	Rango	8
	Rango intercuartil	5
	Asimetría	0.000
	Curtosis	0.893
5	Media	6.00
	95% de intervalo de confianza	Límite inferior 1.79 Límite superior 10.21
	Media recortada al 5%	6.00
	Mediana	7.00
	Varianza	11.500
	Desviación estándar	3.391
	Mínimo	2
	Máximo	10
	Rango	8
	Rango intercuartil	7
	Asimetría	-0.192
	Curtosis	-2.234

Figure 8. Satisfaction

D. Discussion

The results are generally very promising, especially when referring to the pace of development recorded. They announce, therefore, a prosperous future for many improvement operations, as long as promotional strategies obtain a greater degree of rationality. Given the commercial context and competitive restrictions of modern times, the solidarity market is invited to deploy even more efforts with cooperatives that offer solidarity products. Its action should go beyond the simple role of exhibition space to be integrated into a synergistic dynamic based on its participation with the cooperatives in terms of the control and improvement of the quality/quantity of the products, the improvement of transport and storage logistics, the differentiation of health safety standards and market access according to local specificities[32].

The system was carried out under a sequence of phases of the RUP methodology, which It includes a set of methodologies adaptable to the context and needs of the company. The system controls the production of personal hygiene products, classifying natural inputs and essences according to the quality of each product. So same, the sequence in the sales process; registration, search and delivery of product. It was decided to use the PHP web language for coding, which works very well with the database manager. For this reason, the systems are of great help for any commercial transaction, regardless of the product or service in a competitive market[33].

IV. CONCLUSION

The analysis of the impact of PunoMarket on the marketing of rural products in the Puno region has revealed significant results in terms of user satisfaction, user retention, market expansion and profitability for local producers. **User Satisfaction:** The PunoMarket platform has achieved an average satisfaction score of 4.7 out of 5. This indicates that users positively value the ease of use and reliability of the service. This high satisfaction is crucial for the retention and continued growth of the user base.

User Retention Rate: An 80 percent retention rate shows that the majority of users continue to use the platform after their first use. This reflects PunoMarket's effectiveness in providing a satisfying and valuable experience for its users, fostering their loyalty.

Market Expansion: Geographic Location of Users: PunoMarket has attracted users from various regions of Puno, with a notable expansion towards rural areas. This penetration into more remote markets is essential for the sustainable growth of the platform and for rural producers' access to broader markets. **Diversity of Product Categories:** The platform has increased the variety of products sold, including crafts, processed foods and textiles. This diversification is essential to attract a broader consumer base and to offer more sales opportunities to local producers.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. Castilla, A. Pacheco, and J. Franco, "Digital government: Mobile applications and their impact on access to public information," *SoftwareX*, vol. 22, p. 101382, 2023, ISSN: 2352-7110. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2023.101382>. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S235271102300078X>.
- [2] C. Wilson and I. Mergel, "Overcoming barriers to digital government: Mapping the strategies of digital champions," *Government Information Quarterly*, vol. 39, no. 2, p. 101681, 2022.
- [3] A. Mazuera-Rozo, C. Escobar-Velásquez, J. Espitia-Acero, *et al.*, "Taxonomy of security weaknesses in java and kotlin android apps," *Journal of systems and software*, vol. 187, p. 111233, 2022.
- [4] C. Laporte and R. O'Connor, "Systems and software engineering standards for very small entities: Accomplishments and overview," *Computer*, vol. 49, no. 8, pp. 84–87, 2016.
- [5] G. P. Gasca-Hurtado, M. C. Gómez-Álvarez, J. A. Hincapié, and V. V. Zepeda, "Gamification of an educational environment in software engineering: Case study for digital accessibility of people with disabilities," *IEEE Revista Iberoamericana de Tecnologías del Aprendizaje*, vol. 16, no. 4, pp. 382–392, 2021.
- [6] O. E. Tituchina Quillupangui and C. D. Toapanta Rodríguez, "Desarrollo de una aplicación web y móvil para la comercialización de los productos de la mega distribuidora san juan de la ciudad de latacunga.," B.S. thesis, Ecuador: Latacunga: Universidad Técnica de Cotopaxi (UTC), 2021.
- [7] M. Z. Aguinaga Cueva, "Estrategias de distribución en la gestión de la marca artesanía san mateo dirigido al mercado de lima metropolitana," 2018.
- [8] A. C. Lazo Meza and Y. R. Ticse Amancay, "Estudio de pre factibilidad para establecer una fábrica taller de artesanía a base de sojilla para la comercialización en mercados internacionales," 2021.
- [9] J. A. Cabezas Cordova, "Marketing digital y la comercialización de artesanías de las islas de los uros, puno, 2022," 2022.
- [10] D. Y. N. Tintaya, D. M. Yucra, X. Y. J. Ninaja, and W. J. Ramos, "Palabras claves: Tecnologías, comercialización, artesanías.,"
- [11] L. G. J. Medina Alvarez, "Análisis de los factores internos de la oferta exportable de artesanía textil para el ingreso a los mercados internacionales, region puno-periodo 2012," 2013.
- [12] M. P. Pérez Díaz and M. Rivoin López, "Estrategias de promoción para la comercialización de los productos artesanales de algodón nativo en la zona de amortiguamiento del santuario histórico bosque de pómac, pítipo–ferreñafe," 2018.
- [13] J. A. Diaz Mamani, "Producción y comercialización textil en los comerciantes de la laguna temporal de la ciudad de juliaca, provincia san román, región puno, 2020," 2021.
- [14] C. R. Sanz Moya, E. G. Rosas Cruz, E. J. Arroyo Flores, and D. F. Araca Perez, "Modelo prolab: Paqu, una app de propuesta sostenible para diversificar los ingresos de los alpaqueros de la ciudad de ayaviri, provincia melgar, departamento de puno,"
- [15] P. M. Leon Santa Cruz and R. Y. Perez Vigo, "Marketing digital para incrementar la comercialización de productos artesanales de la asociación de artesanos llampayec, lambayeque–2021," 2022.
- [16] E. Carhuamaca Hospinal, N. Chacón Buendía, R. Meza Soria, and V. G. Roig Aranibar, "Planeamiento estratégico del sector artesanía de la región ayacucho," 2012.
- [17] T. K. Sheng and P. Subramanian, "Proposition of rank-based stepwise interactive visualization for customer segmentation in e-commerce," in *Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Software Engineering and Information Management*, 2019, pp. 244–248.
- [18] M. Elena, "Observatorio ecommerce y transformación digital," *Obtenido de: <https://observatorioecommerce.com/como-crece-el-comercioelectronico-en-el-mundo/empresarial>*, vol. 21, 2018.
- [19] Y. Arregui Bedoya, "Artisanale. conceptualización y diseño de plataforma de productos artesanales," 2018.
- [20] M. Pritchard, "Commentary: "half my digital advertising is wasted..."," *Journal of Marketing*, vol. 85, no. 1, pp. 26–29, 2021.
- [21] J. Quevedo, O. Fortich, and S. Tapias, "Diseño e implementación de una plataforma móvil que permita impulsar el comercio de productos artesanales hechos por campesinos colombianos," 2021.
- [22] G. M. Prats, V. J. Cervantes, and F. S. Hernández, "Comercio electrónico como medio de estrategia para el impulso de productos artesanales," *Revista de Investigación Académica Sin Frontera: Facultad Interdisciplinaria de Ciencias Económicas Administrativas-Departamento de Ciencias Económico Administrativas-Campus Navojoa*, no. 35, 2021.
- [23] A. Ceron, R. J. R. Reyes, H. C. Islas, *et al.*, "La importancia de la investigación," *Boletín Científico De Las Ciencias Económico Administrativas Del ICEA*, vol. 9, no. 17, pp. 49–50, 2020.
- [24] S. H. Mendoza, D. D. Avila, *et al.*, "Técnicas e instrumentos de recolección de datos," *Boletín científico de las ciencias económico administrativas del ICEA*, vol. 9, no. 17, pp. 51–53, 2020.
- [25] D. G. Lubas, "System and software cost correlation to reliability," in *2016 Annual Reliability and Maintainability Symposium (RAMS)*, IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–6.
- [26] J. Jaimes, E. K. T. Diaz, I. F. B. Bravo, J. C. C. Aldaz, J. A. C. Chaglla, and N. Y. P. Rivas, "Análisis de datos en el cuidado de elaeis guineensis (palma

africana) en Colombia, Ecuador y Perú,” *Revista Ciencia y Tecnología*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 35–42, 2023.

- [27] W. A. Ruesta, R. Q. Fernández, C. L. J. Rivero, and R. M. C. Urbina, “Condiciones culturales y socioeconómicas de las caletas pesqueras artesanales en Yacila y Carquín, Perú,” *Revista de la Universidad del Zulia*, vol. 14, no. 41, pp. 58–81, 2023.
- [28] M. Preciado Céspedes, “Gestión administrativa, impacto en la responsabilidad social en la municipalidad distrital de San Jacinto, Región Tumbes, Perú, 2022.” 2022.
- [29] C. Constante Saavedra, “Modelo de negocio “Ecuacrafts Shopping”: Plataforma digital para artesanos,” B.S. thesis, Universidad Casa Grande. Facultad de Administración y Negocios, 2024.
- [30] C. G. Rivera Adriano and Y. N. Trujillo Nacion, “Costos de producción y la fijación de precios de los productores de cerámica en arcilla de la Asociación de Artesanos del Distrito de Tápuc Provincia Daniel Alcides Carrión, periodo 2021,” 2024.
- [31] D.-C. Cárdenas-Damián, J.-A. Álvarez-Cedillo, A. Rodríguez-Rodríguez, and T. Álvarez-Sánchez, “Comportamiento del consumidor en la valoración y apreciación de productos artesanales mexicanos a través del social marketing,” *RIDE. Revista Iberoamericana para la Investigación y el Desarrollo Educativo*, vol. 14, no. 27, 2023.
- [32] A. El Bakkali, Y. Fridi, S. El Kouraich, and A. Ouazani, “Mercados solidarios en Marruecos: Plataformas creativas para la comercialización de productos cooperativos. caso de la provincia de Larache,” 2024.
- [33] E. J. Garrido Vasquez, “Sistema web de control de producción y venta para la empresa Marbella, Cajamarca,” 2023.